

EXPERIMENTAL MODAL ANALYSIS OF NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED ACRYLONITRILE-BUTADIENE-STYRENE (ABS) THERMOPLASTIC BIOCOMPOSITES

Arař. Gör., Osman ÖZENÇ¹, Doç. Dr., Mirali NURALIYEV², Dr. Öğr. Üyesi, Mehmet Akif DÜNDAR³, Doç. Dr. Davut Erdem ŞAHİN⁴

¹Yozgat Bozok University, College of Engineering, - 0000-0003-3455-9411

²Yozgat Bozok University, College of Engineering, - 0000-0002-3063-8414

³Yozgat Bozok University, College of Engineering, - 0000-0001-5463-6774

⁴Yalova University, College of Engineering, - 0000-0001-6770-7252

ABSTRACT

A very limited exploratory research has been conducted to elucidate the natural particle addition effects on the dynamic characteristics of polymers including natural frequency, mode shape, and damping ratio. In response to this, the present study has been dedicated to the examination of the effect of added hemp fiber particles on the modal parameters of an industrially important Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) thermoplastic. Biocomposites were fabricated by incorporating hemp particles into ABS at three various weight fractions (1%, 5%, and 10 %). Modal testing aiming to measure the associated dynamic modal parameters was performed on both the rectangular neat ABS and ABS biocomposites with a dimension of 120x145 mm by using a roving impact hammer method with a fixed response measurement point. A one-edge clamped boundary condition was successfully applied to the testing specimens. The modal test results revealed that the incorporation of hemp particles generally enhances the modal parameters of neat ABS such as the first three natural frequencies and associated damping ratios. The experimental results also put forth that the mentioned modal parameters tend to improve considerably with increasing particle content. Regardless of the particle weight fraction, it was found that the incorporation of hemp particles possesses an insignificant influence on the patterns of the first three mode shapes of neat ABS.

Keywords: Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS), Hemp, Biocomposites, Experimental modal analysis, Natural frequency, Mode shape, Damping ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer materials have been used for various applications for over a century. The invention of synthetic polymers in the 20th century revolutionized the industry due to their low cost, versatility, and easy processing. Polymers find wide-ranging applications in various industries,

including but not limited to the automotive, packaging, construction, and electronics industries. Among them, The Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) copolymer, formed by the combination of acrylonitrile, butadiene, and styrene monomers, is extensively utilized in various industries owing to its exceptional mechanical properties such as high impact resistance, stiffness, toughness, and good dimensional stability[1–3]. The properties of the ABS polymer are greatly influenced by the concentration and arrangement of these monomers. The ratio of these monomers in the polymer chain can be adjusted to tailor the material properties according to the desired application[4]. Besides, addition of reinforcing materials such as fibers or particles enhances the strength, stiffness, and toughness of ABS [5–11].

The environmental damage caused by the waste of ABS and other synthetic chemical materials produced in a similar manner has become an undeniable problem in today's world, in parallel with the increasing volume of their use. ABS has been identified as a possible environmental hazard owing to its non-biodegradable nature. When disposed of improperly, ABS can contribute to plastic pollution in the environment. Moreover, when burned, ABS can release hazardous chemicals such as styrene and acrylonitrile, leading to air pollution and associated health risks[1,12]. Therefore, natural fiber-reinforced ABS composites have gained popularity due to their sustainability and eco-friendliness[13–18]. The addition of natural fibers, such as kenaf, palm, bamboo etc., to ABS improves its mechanical properties and reduces its negative environmental impact[19–21].

The modal parameters, also known as dynamic parameters, play an important role in industrial applications. The dynamic properties of materials, such as natural frequencies, damping ratios and mode shapes, are essential in determining the structural behavior of the material. The natural frequency of a polymer provides information on its stiffness, while the damping ratio indicates its energy dissipation capacity. These parameters are crucial for the design and analysis of structures to ensure their performance and reliability[22–24].

This study aimed to experimentally demonstrate the dynamic characteristics of the newly developed environmentally friendly and sustainable hemp particle-reinforced ABS biocomposite plates. To this end, rectangular plates with a thickness of 4mm were produced by incorporating hemp particles to ABS at different weight fractions including 1%, 5%, and 10%. An injection molding technique was used in the production of biocomposites.

Modal analyses aiming to measure the dynamic parameters including damping ratios, natural frequencies, and associated modal shapes, were performed on the one edge clamped plates by deploying a roving impact hammer technique with a fixed response measurement point. Applying the widely accepted half-power bandwidth method to the measured frequency response function (FRF) data, damping ratios were computed for each plate[25–28]. The effects of the addition of hemp particles on the dynamic parameters of ABS were elucidated by the experimental findings.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Dew retted and crushed industrial hemp stems (*Cannabis sativa*) were brought from the Vezirköprü district of Samsun province, Turkey, provided by the Vezirköprü District Agricultural of Forestry Department, which was cultivated in the region. According to official reports, the density of hemp fibers was recorded as 760 kg/m^3 . ABS granules (LG Chem Company HI121H) were sourced from local supplier RİİZ Makina corporation limited, TURKEY. The reported relative density of the ABS granules is 1040 kg/m^3 (ASTM D792), and their melting flow rate, under a 10 kg load at $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, is 23 g/10 min (ASTM D1238). Furthermore, SEBS-g-MA (Styrene-Ethylene/Butylene-Styrene-Maleic anhydride-graft) obtained from Kraton Company (KRATON™ FG1901 G) was utilized for better adhesion between ABS and hemp fiber particles.

Dew-retted and crushed stems of industrial hemp were subjected to decortication in order to separate the hemp bast fibers from the hurds. After the aforementioned operations, the obtained hemp fibers were fragmented to a length of approximately 10 cm and subjected to a pre-washing process by soaking them in purified water at room temperature for a duration of 24 hours to remove any dirt and dust particles present in the fibers. After the pre-washing process, the hemp fibers were dried in a clean environment at room temperature with regular intervals while being stirred, and then subjected to an alkaline surface cleaning process by soaking them in a 10% NaOH solution prepared with distilled water at room temperature for one day. The hemp fibers, which had been subjected to an alkaline treatment to remove unwanted substances such as lignin and pectin and to improve their bonding with ABS, were washed with purified water and dried at room temperature in the clean environment[19,29–31]. The alkaline treated hemp fibers, which had been purified from unwanted components such as lignin and pectin, were dried in an oven at 100°C for one hour and subsequently fragmented into particles smaller than 1mm by using a high-speed blender (35000 rpm) for at least 15 minutes.

Figure 1. Production process of ABS/Hemp biocomposite plate specimens.

The processed hemp fiber particles were mixed with SEBS-g-MA in a weight ratio of 92:8, and then the resulting mixture was mechanically blended with ABS at weight ratios of 1%, 5%, and 10% for at least 15 minutes for each. For better reading 1%, 5%, and 10% hemp added ABS specimens will be coded as Hemp-1, Hemp-5 and Hemp-10 respectively. The mixtures obtained from the mechanical blending were further processed using a co-rotated twin-screw extruder about 190°C to obtain biocomposite pellets. A twin-screw extruder machine was used to confirm a homogeneous mixture of hemp fiber particles, ABS, and SEBS-g-MA before the production of ABS-Hemp biocomposite plate specimens by injection molding. The obtained biocomposite pellets were injected into a mold with dimensions of 145x145x4mm at a temperature of 200°C, which was chosen to avoid thermal degradation, to produce test specimens. All production process of ABS-Hemp biocomposite plates have been introduced schematically in Figure 1.

Method

In order to determine the dynamic parameters of the produced ABS-Hemp biocomposite plates, a modal analysis was conducted using the roving hammer method. In order to obtain accurate modal analysis data, the hammer hit points were determined by marking on a 120 x 145 mm area on plate specimen as shown in Figure 2. The identical plate test layout and hammer hit points were modeled in Pulse LabShop software, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Determined hammer hit points on plate specimens

Figure 3. Hammer hit points and measurement sequence on Pulse LabShop software.

The experimental test setup with one edge fixed boundary condition to a rigid clamp table for plate specimen is indicated in Figure 4. Acceleration data was measured with Brüel&Kjaer 4513B single axis accelerometer during modal analysis. The accelerometer was mounted on the plate specimens utilizing honey as illustrated in Figure 4. Specimen impact force excitation was implemented with Brüel&Kjaer type 8206-002 impact hammer. The Pulse LabShop 14.1 software was used to analyze the modal test data obtained from an impact hammer and accelerometer using a Brüel&Kjaer type 3050-B-060 6 channel data acquisition (DAQ) device.

Figure 4. Experimental test setup for modal analysis.

Hammer hit excitations were performed 3 times on each point and time acceleration data was collected by Pulse LabShop 14.1 software with the help of Brüel&Kjaer 3050-B-060 DAQ device in the sequence depicted in the Figure 3. Frequency Response Function (FRF) of each point was calculated by Pulse LabShop software by averaging 3 hit acceleration data to attain more accurate results. By considering the FRF data of each point along the plate model, the natural frequencies and associated mode shapes were obtained in the software. Furthermore, associated damping ratios of first three natural frequencies were calculated from FRF data using the half-power damping method. Damping ratio calculation by this method detailedly shown in Figure 5 involves determining the bandwidth of the FRF at the half-power point, which corresponds to the frequency at which the amplitude of the response is half of its maximum value. The damping ratio can be computed by dividing the half-power bandwidth of the system by its resonance frequency.

Figure 5. Damping ratio calculation with Half-Power bandwidth method.

The expression for the calculation of damping ratio (c) can be given as follows:

$$c = \frac{\omega_2 - \omega_1}{2\omega_n} \quad (1)$$

Where ω_n is the natural frequency corresponding the peak amplitude A_n . Moreover, ω_1 and ω_2 are the frequencies corresponding the amplitudes A_1 and A_2 , respectively. It is a fact that A_1 and A_2 are identical to each other, and both can be computed with the following expression.

$$A_{1,2} = \frac{A_n}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (2)$$

By utilizing this method, we can accurately quantify the damping ratio of the plate specimens to put forward its dynamic behavior for further analyses.

RESULTS

The frequency response function (FRF) results of neat and hemp biocomposite plate specimens were obtained by using the roving hammer method on the experimental setup are presented in Figure 6. Subsequently, the first three natural frequencies obtained through the modal analysis of the plate specimens are given in Table 1.

Figure 6. FRFs comparison of the plate specimens extracted from experimental modal analysis.

As can be understood from Table 1 and Figure 6, the natural frequencies of hemp fiber-added biocomposite specimens are always higher than the natural frequencies of neat ABS in each natural frequency mode.

Table 1. Natural frequencies of neat and hemp biocomposite plates from modal analysis.

	Natural Frequencies (Hz)		
	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3
Neat ABS	67.5	139	379.5
Hemp-1	70.5	146	398.5
Hemp-5	69.5	144.5	394
Hemp-10	68.5	143	391.5

Therefore, it can be seen that the addition of hemp fibers increases the rigidity of the neat ABS material and consequently leads to an increase in the natural frequencies of biocomposite materials. This difference between natural frequencies becomes more pronounced at higher frequencies, as can be clearly seen in Table 1. Although it has been observed that the addition of hemp fibers increases the natural frequencies of neat ABS, it has been also revealed that the increase in natural frequencies decreases with the increasing amount of hemp fiber particle addition.

Figure 7. First three mode shapes obtained from experimental modal analysis for plate specimens.

In terms of mode shapes, the 1st and 3rd mode shapes correspond to the 1st and 2nd bending modes, respectively, while the 2nd mode shape corresponds to the 1st twisting mode. After examining the mode shapes in experimental results, it can be concluded that the addition of hemp fiber particles to ABS did not cause any change the overall mode shapes.

Table 2 presents the damping ratios associated to the first three natural frequencies obtained through the half-power bandwidth method for the plate specimens. Upon examining the damping ratios, it is clear that the damping ratios for the second modes slightly increased compared to the first modes but decreased at the third modes. Additionally, it can be seen that the addition of hemp fiber particle to ABS increased the damping ratio as the percentage of hemp increased, except for a small decrease observed in Hemp-1 compared to neat ABS at

second and third modes. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that the incorporation of hemp fiber into the ABS polymer material results in improved damping properties.

Table 2. Damping ratios for the first three natural frequencies

	Damping Ratios (%)		
	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3
Neat ABS	0.968	1.070	0.996
Hemp-1	0.995	1.007	0.948
Hemp-5	1.122	1.157	1.089
Hemp-10	1.208	1.320	1.137

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Alkaline treated hemp fiber particle added ABS with SEBS-g-MA at three different weight ratios (%1, %5 and %10) biocomposite plates were produced by injection molding to investigate their dynamic parameters. Natural frequencies and associated mode shapes of neat and hemp fiber added plate specimens were determined with experimental modal analysis utilizing roving hammer method and damping ratios were defined with half-power bandwidth method. The following conclusions can be drawn from the experimental results as:

Comparing the biocomposite materials produced with hemp fiber particle addition to neat ABS, it is observed that the fiber particle addition increases the rigidity of the materials and causes an increase in their natural frequencies.

Although the natural frequencies of the materials change with the addition of hemp fiber, the mode shapes of the first three natural frequencies were not affected and were found to be similar.

It was observed from the findings that the damping ratios corresponding to the second mode increased compared to the first mode damping ratios. Besides, it was observed that the third mode damping ratios decreased more than the first mode damping ratio values. Furthermore, the results indicate that that addition of hemp fiber particles increased the damping ratio compared to neat ABS. Hence, the hemp fiber particle addition increased the energy absorption capacity of the neat ABS copolymer material, making it more damping material.

REFERENCES

1. Olivera S, Muralidhara HB, Venkatesh K, Gopalakrishna K, Vivek CS. Plating on acrylonitrile–butadiene–styrene (ABS) plastic: a review. *Journal of Materials Science*. 2016;51(8):3657–74.
2. Yousefi M, Gholamian F, Ghanbari D, Salavati-Niasari M. Polymeric nanocomposite materials: Preparation and characterization of star-shaped PbS nanocrystals and their influence on the thermal stability of acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) copolymer. *Polyhedron* [Internet]. 2011;30(6):1055–60. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.poly.2011.01.012>
3. Kamelian FS, Saljoughi E, Shojaee Nasirabadi P, Mousavi SM. Modifications and research potentials of acrylonitrile/butadiene/styrene (ABS) membranes: A review. *Polymer Composites*. 2018;39(8):2835–46.
4. Moore J. Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) - a review. *Composites* [Internet]. 1973 May;4(3):118–30. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0010436173905855>
5. H R M, Benal MGM, G S P, Tambrallimath V, Ramaiah K, Khan TMY, et al. Effect of Short Glass Fiber Addition on Flexural and Impact Behavior of 3D Printed Polymer Composites. *ACS Omega* [Internet]. 2023 Mar 14;8(10):9212–20. Available from: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsomega.2c07227>
6. Dhandapani A, Krishnasamy S, Nagarajan R, Selvaraj ADA, Thiagamani SMK, Muthukumar C, et al. Investigation of Wear Behavior in Self-Lubricating ABS Polymer Composites Reinforced with Glass Fiber/ABS and Glass Fiber/Carbon Fiber/ABS Hybrid. *Lubricants* [Internet]. 2023 Mar 13;11(3):131. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4442/11/3/131>
7. Zahid A, Anwar MT, Ahmed A, Raza Y, Gohar GA, Jamshaid M. Synthesis and Investigation of Mechanical Properties of the Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene Fiber Composites Using Fused Deposition Modeling. *3D Printing and Additive Manufacturing* [Internet]. 2023 Jan 30; Available from: <https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/3dp.2022.0199>
8. Young D, Wetmore N, Czabaj M. Interlayer fracture toughness of additively manufactured unreinforced and carbon-fiber-reinforced acrylonitrile butadiene styrene. *Additive Manufacturing* [Internet]. 2018 Aug;22(February):508–15. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.02.023>
9. Kumar P, Palsule S. Bamboo Fiber Reinforced Chemically Functionalized Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene Composites by Palsule Process. *Journal of Natural Fibers* [Internet]. 2023;20(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2022.2150741>
10. Sahu S, Sahu SBBPJ, Nayak S, Roul MK, Khuntia SK. Effect of chemical treatment and fiber loading on various properties of Bauhinia vahlii bast fibers/acrylonitrile butadiene styrene composites for automotive body parts. *Polymer Composites* [Internet]. 2022 Aug 20;43(8):4909–18. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pc.26751>

11. Chauhan V, Kärki T, Varis J. Effect of Fiber Content and Silane Treatment on the Mechanical Properties of Recycled Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene Fiber Composites. Chemistry [Internet]. 2021 Nov 1;3(4):1258–70. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1944/14/9/2223>
12. Rutkowski J V, Levin B. Pyrolysis and Combustion Products and their Toxicity-A Review of the Literature. Fire Mater. 1986;10(July):93–105.
13. Chotirat L, Chaochanchaikul K, Sombatsompop N. On adhesion mechanisms and interfacial strength in acrylonitrile–butadiene–styrene/wood sawdust composites. International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives [Internet]. 2007 Dec;27(8):669–78. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0143749607000309>
14. Threepopnatkul P, Krachang T, Teerawattananon W, Suriyaphaparkorn K, Kulsetthanchalee C. Study of surface treatment of pineapple leaf fiber (PALF) on performance of PALF/ABS composites. ECCM 2012 - Composites at Venice, Proceedings of the 15th European Conference on Composite Materials. 2012;(June):24–8.
15. Akato K, Tran CD, Chen J, Naskar AK. Poly(ethylene oxide)-Assisted Macromolecular Self-Assembly of Lignin in ABS Matrix for Sustainable Composite Applications. ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering [Internet]. 2015 Dec 7;3(12):3070–6. Available from: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acssuschemeng.5b00509>
16. Obianuju OH. Mechanical Properties, Morphology and Elemental Composition of Composites Produced from Thermoplastic Polymers Filled with Egg Shell. International Research Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry [Internet]. 2021 Mar 9;22(1):59–78. Available from: <https://www.journalirjpac.com/index.php/IRJPAC/article/view/30374>
17. Ponsuriyaprakash S, Udhayakumar P, Pandiyarajan R. Experimental Investigation of ABS Matrix and Cellulose Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite Materials. Journal of Natural Fibers [Internet]. 2020 Nov 9;00(00):1–12. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15440478.2020.1841065>
18. Neher B, Bhuiyan MMR, Kabir H, Gafur MA, Ahmed F. Fabrication and Optical Characterization of Palm Fiber Reinforced Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene Based Composites: Band Gap Studies. Materials Sciences and Applications. 2018;09(02):246–57.
19. Ma L, He H, Jiang C, Zhou L, Luo Y, Jia D. Effect of Alkali Treatment on Structure and Mechanical Properties of Acrylonitrile–Butadiene–Styrene/Bamboo Fiber Composites. Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part B [Internet]. 2012 Nov 2;51(11):2232–44. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00222348.2012.669688>
20. Mohammad NB, Arsad A. Mechanical, Thermal and Morphological Study of Kenaf Fibre Reinforced rPET/ABS composites. Malaysian Polymer Journal [Internet]. 2013;8(1):8–13. Available from: www.cheme.utm.my/mpj
21. Neher B, Bhuiyan MMR, Kabir H, Qadir MR, Gafur MA, Ahmed F. Study of Mechanical and Physical Properties of Palm Fiber Reinforced Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene Composite. Materials Sciences and Applications [Internet]. 2014;05(01):39–45. Available from: <http://www.scirp.org/journal/doi.aspx?DOI=10.4236/msa.2014.51006>

22. Ewins DJ. Modal Testing: Theory, Practice and Application. 2001;562. Available from: <http://www.amazon.com/Modal-Testing-Application-Mechanical-Engineering/dp/0863802184>
23. Jinguang Z, Hairu Y, Guozhi C, Zeng Z. Structure and modal analysis of carbon fiber reinforced polymer raft frame. *Journal of Low Frequency Noise Vibration and Active Control*. 2018;37(3):577–89.
24. Avitabile P. Modal Testing: A Practitioner's Guide [Internet]. *Modal Testing: A Practitioner's Guide*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons Ltd; 2017. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/9781119222989>
25. Sun P, Wang D. Comparison of damping parameters based on the half-power bandwidth methods of viscous and hysteretic damping models. *JVC/Journal of Vibration and Control*. 2023;29(3–4):968–79.
26. Zhu C, Zhuang Y, Fan W, Long Z, Zhang S. A novel evaluation method for rolling energy losses of tacked vehicle road wheels using experimental modal analysis. *Journal of Terramechanics* [Internet]. 2023;106:47–56. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jterra.2022.12.003>
27. Lacarbonara W, Guruva SK, Carboni B, Krause B, Janke A, Formica G, et al. Unusual nonlinear switching in branched carbon nanotube nanocomposites. *Scientific Reports* [Internet]. 2023;1–12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-32331-y>
28. Nandwani S, Vardhan S, Bahl S, Yadav AK, Samyal R, Bagha AK. Evaluating the dynamic characteristics of microwave-casted metal matrix composite material by using experimental modal analysis. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering* [Internet]. 2023 Feb 28;095440892311589. Available from: <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/09544089231158921>
29. Liu H, You L, Jin H, Yu W. Influence of alkali treatment on the structure and properties of hemp fibers. *Fibers and Polymers* [Internet]. 2013 Mar 6;14(3):389–95. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s12221-013-0389-8>
30. George J, Sreekala MS, Thomas S. A review on interface modification and characterization of natural fiber reinforced plastic composites. *Polymer Engineering and Science*. 2001;41(9):1471–85.
31. Ku H, Wang H, Pattarachaiyakoop N, Trada M. A review on the tensile properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites. *Composites Part B: Engineering*. 2011;42(4):856–73.